

The Next Billion Dollar StartUp

What strategies do entrepreneurs need to become Fortune 500 companies?

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Abstract

This paper examines the strategies that enable startups to grow into Fortune 500 companies, drawing lessons from both successful and failed ventures. It explores the foundational role of entrepreneurial motivation, mission-driven design, and agile operating models in scaling early-stage companies into billion-dollar enterprises. Through analysis of case studies such as Apple, Amazon, and Tesla, as well as empirical research on startup survival rates, the study identifies critical patterns of opportunity recognition, resource mobilization, and organizational design. The paper also evaluates common pitfalls such as market misalignment, funding constraints, and execution gaps, offering guidance for entrepreneurs seeking sustainable growth in competitive markets.

Keywords

Startups; Entrepreneurship; Fortune 500; Business Strategy; Innovation; Technology Management; Venture Growth

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“What strategies do entrepreneurs need to become Fortune 500 companies?”

Entrepreneurship is a term synonymous with StartUps. So, what exactly is a Startup? Start-ups are companies, enterprises, or ventures that are often formed by an individual or a group of individuals who want to develop a product, business, or service. When we think of a startup, we imagine someone living in their parents' basement, working from their garage, or starting out from their college dorm, however a five to six year old company can still be considered a startup. Many of the world's largest corporations, including Microsoft, Disney, Apple, and Amazon, among others all started out in a garage as an idea from from a budding entrepreneur.

This paper seeks to explore what it took for those startups to grow to Fortune 500 companies, specifically what strategies successful "fortune 500 startups" used in scaling up and growing. We would investigate the pitfalls, contexts, similarities, and parallel processes used by the entrepreneurs during the early stages of the startup's journey. This research would also examine unsuccessful entrepreneurs and failed startups in order to identify potential pitfalls to avoid and strategies that must be put in place to increase the likelihood of success when establishing a startup as a new entrepreneur.

Introduction

Currently, "as of the time of writing this paper," there are approximately 135 companies valued at more than a billion dollars. The chances of any new venture, also known as a startup, achieving a valuation of more than a billion dollars are so slim that accomplishing the feat earns you the moniker Unicorn, “a technology startup company that reaches a \$1 billion market value as determined by private or public investment”(Pride, 2018). Small businesses and startups are significant contributors to the growth and success of any economy (Henrekson & Johansson, 2010; Pugliese et al., 2016). They frequently create a sizeable but disproportionate number of jobs.

However, the success and growth of startups is dependent on a variety of factors. All too often, we see startups that have previously demonstrated growth potential fizzle out. (Yin, 2012) points out in a Wall Street Journal article that startups fail in greater numbers and at much higher rates than current industry projections. A great deal of research and literature has been produced to highlight the success of a few companies (Microsoft, Apple, and Google), all of which began as startups and have since grown to become multibillion-dollar corporations (Feinleib, 2012). Furthermore, they fail to elaborate on the strategies used by entrepreneurs and founders to achieve success, as well as the mistakes they made and pitfalls they avoided. All key decisions that led to their companies' eventual success and growth into billion dollar corporations.

Today's industry accepts that three or four out of every ten ventures or startups fail, and this has gradually become a rite of passage for every aspiring entrepreneur (Yin , 2012; Pride, 2018). When venture capitalists make investments, they do so with the expectation that the majority of them will fail and only a few will succeed. As a result, it is critical that we critically examine successful entrepreneurs and the approaches they used to succeed in this age of constant change and disruption. Understanding the approaches of entrepreneurs who have successfully produced billion-dollar companies allows us to try to replicate their approach; this does not guarantee success in our venture, but it does reduce the risk of failure.

Formation of Startups

One of the most difficult things you can undertake as an individual is translating an abstract thought into physical reality. The process of transforming a concept from imagination into a tangible object needless to say is in and of itself the art of creation. Now, let us contextualize this process, every billion dollar corporation, every company started as an idea, a dream, a desire to create. Some creations were born out of necessity. One such invention is the “wheel” which is believed to have been developed in Lower Mesopotamia (present-day Iraq) during the fourth millennium BC. Someone must have thought, "Ahh, wouldn't it be simple to be able to move from A to B exerting as minimal force as required but covering a greater distance” maybe not in so much detail but our point remains. The abstraction, the concept became reality.

In today's world, we see and experience the same phenomenon. A majority of the billion-dollar corporations all began with an idea. Apple Computers, Inc., a 2.54 trillion dollar company (Fig. 1), began with the idea of making computers small enough for people to keep in their homes or offices. Amazon.com, a \$985+ billion dollar company (Fig. 1), began with the idea of simplifying the purchasing experience and leveraging the internet to sell products, Google, whose parent company is Alphabet a 1.135 Trillion dollar corporation (Fig. 1) began with the mission “to organize the world's information and make it universally accessible and useful.”. These are just a few examples of businesses that all began small and, despite how intimidating they may seem, all began as startups with a concept that was not motivated by the need for high financial returns or the desire to simply not be an employee "Be my own boss.". Each of these concepts addressed a specific need or offered a solution to an underlying issue. Therefore, it follows that an entrepreneur must have the right motivations if they want to grow their startup to a billion-dollar valuation. This is our first strategy ***“Having the right motivation behind your Idea”***.

The \$1 trillion club

Apple, Microsoft, Amazon, and Alphabet are worth a combined \$4.7T

SOURCE: FactSet. Data as of 1/31/2020.

Fig 1: Valuations (Apple, Amazon and Alphabet) (Sheetz, 2020)

Challenges and Opportunities of Entrepreneurs

Who will then be able to nurture the next billion-dollar startup? Is it possible for anyone to become an entrepreneur? Is it possible to learn how to be an entrepreneur? We have all had great ideas at some point in our lives, but very few of us pursue or act on them (Baisya, 2021). Based on my experience, I have come to realize that entrepreneurship necessitates a willingness to take risks that may be beyond our acceptance threshold. In our previous section we got to understand that turning abstract ideas into reality is one of the most difficult tasks anyone can pursue. To accomplish this feat however as an entrepreneur certain steps need to be taken from your “Aha! Moment” ideation stage to an eventual Exit (Riani, 2022). Entrepreneurs must have a variety of personality traits if they are to thrive, including dedication, focus, high risk tolerance, resilience, enthusiasm, and patience to travel often risky and less traveled paths in the journey of product development (Baisya, 2021). Taking a business from inception to birth is easier said than done. According to separate studies by the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics and the Ewing Marion Kauffman Foundation, a nonprofit which promotes entrepreneurship about 60% of start-ups survive to age three and roughly 30 - 35% survive to age 10.

Net change in the number of establishments by age of firm in 2019

Hover over chart to view data.
Source: U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics.

Fig 2: Changes in the total number of establishments by age of firm (Sadeghi, 2022)

By March 2019, the total number of businesses in the American economy had increased by 130,015 units. This increase was brought about by the closure of 294,552 already-existing businesses and the opening of 424,567 new businesses. Businesses with a lifespan of 1 to 4 years suffered the greatest establishment loss (Sadeghi, 2022).

Our startup failure numbers indicated in Fig. 2 above suggest that maybe not everyone should be an entrepreneur, as there is a potential 60-70% startup failure rate within the first four years. In addition to this Prior industry experience does not still guarantee success in starting up a venture. Karim Lakhani from MIT after conducting an extensive analysis into the Startup Innocentive highlighted that the probability of success for startups increased in situations where founders or entrepreneurs had no prior or formal expertise in the field under consideration (Baisya, 2021).

Successful entrepreneurs like Steve Jobs (Apple Inc.), Elon Musk (Tesla), a pioneer in the electric vehicle automotive industry, and Richard Branson (Virgin Atlantic), a pioneer in the aviation industry, all came from backgrounds outside of their respective fields. Jobs, who had a variety of interests, Musk, who has a degree in physics, and Branson, who owned a record store, all shared the trait of being outsiders to their fields. The truth is that great entrepreneurs discover great markets. For those markets, they create world-class products. They build efficient organizations capable of bringing those products to market—execution machines that outperform the competition (Feinleib, 2012). This brings us to our second strategy “***Have a Mission-Driven Design***”. A mission-driven strategy ensures entrepreneur prioritize on outcomes rather than fulfilling roles. A focus on mission leads naturally to empowering people to solve problems. Simply put, the strategy takes advantage of opportunities and problems as they materialize. By doing this, learning and, ultimately, business success, are accelerated.

Jobs and Musk are ideal candidates in highlighting the effects of implementing this strategy. 10 years after its formation Apple had grown from just the two people in a garage into a \$2 billion company with over 4,000 employees. However, it was not all smooth sailing, Jobs who founded the company with his friend Steve Wozniak got fired. Apple had grown into a multimillion dollar company and with that comes venture capitalists and investors (Board of Directors). The board of directors had hired PepsiCo CEO John Sculley, whom they thought would be very talented to run the company alongside Jobs. However, their visions for the company's future diverged, and the Board ended up siding with Sculley and ousting Jobs. Jobs spent the next five years starting and founding another company, NeXT computers, whose potential was so good that Apple ended up buying NeXT computers and bringing Jobs back (Jobs, 2005). The board did this in an attempt to rebuild Apple after a massive stock sale sunk the company's stock price. Job's design strategy was mission-driven, which Sculley, who later praised Jobs' effective leadership, calling him "the greatest CEO ever," could not see at the time. Job's mission-driven design focused on creating products that resonated with the average consumer and in doing so created brand loyalty.

Musk's Tesla, on the other hand, was not an overnight success like Apple. Musk took an unconventional approach to assuming his role as the face of Tesla, and some would argue founder. Prior to Tesla, Musk had successfully launched and sold a number of startups. Notably, he co-founded PayPal, which was later sold to eBay in 2002. He also founded Space X, a company that designs spacecraft and advanced rockets, Zip2, an online publishing company, and X.com, an online bank that was acquired by Confinity. Musk is a serial entrepreneur who uses a mission-driven design approach to create products that address specific outcomes. Following the initial rounds of funding, Musk joined the Tesla Board of Directors, eventually becoming CEO and positioning the company so that its products are not only among the best in the industry, but also addresses a specific niche market. This approach increased customer brand loyalty, which not only grew the brand but also ensured the company's success.

Why do startups fail

To begin, let us first consider why startups fail, CB Insights, a business analytics platform and global database that offers private companies and investors market intelligence, thorough data, expert insights, and work management tools in order to spur growth and enhance operations, recently conducted an analysis on more than 110 startups by reviewing their failure post-mortems (CB Insights, 2021).

This data-driven analysis of why most startups fail, as shown in Fig. 3, highlights 12 reasons why startups fail. We can see that 38% of failures were due to a lack of capital/cash, and 35% were due to a lack of market demand for the service, product, or good. It is obvious that startups need to fully understand how money and funding determine their businesses' success, and as a result, they should concentrate on making that money easily accessible through angel investments, crowdsourcing, etc.

Lack of "Market" demand for the product is also one of the major contributors to a startups failure. In addition to being able to respond to the question of why someone would be willing to pay for this product, all startups should be able to state with clarity why the product is needed and whether it is actually required for the target market. Thus, why now? The third alarming reason we see is "Got Outcompeted"

Fig 3: Reasons Startups fail (CB Insights, 2021)

Funding and cash burn have a direct correlation with competition. By choosing simple targets (seriously unhappy users of competing products) and developing a cost-controlled market entry strategy, one could reduce the amount of cash expended by generating income. While many

entrepreneurs and startups can boast of successful ventures in this era of constant change and disruption, a significant number are faced with the reality of failure because the founder or entrepreneur was unable to handle pressure and manage uncertainty (Tomy & Pardede, 2018).

Entrepreneurial Venture Creation

Josph Schumpeter in his 1947 article “*The Creative Response in Economic History*” economy in the Journal of Economic History was concerned with the correlation between entrepreneurship and the economy. He made the point that the forces driving economic change in any capitalist economy depend on entrepreneurial activity, and that opportunities in capitalist society are thus a direct result of entrepreneurship (Schumpeter, 1947). Baisya, 2021 defines Entrepreneurship thus, the task of an entrepreneur is “Creative Destruction” based on Schumpeter's analysis. A 2001 Study was conducted by a doctoral candidate at MIT's Sloan School of Management; and Scott Stern, associate professor of management and strategy at Northwestern University's Kellogg School of Management, Joshua S. Gans, professor of management at Melbourne Business School; David H. Hsu, to investigate Schumpeter’s theory on when the entrepreneurial process through startups spur creative destruction (Kwak, 2002). The investigators identified two options for potential new entrants and startups during the venture creation process. 1.) Compete with established companies for the product market share, 2.) Cooperate with established companies by selling their products through the market (i.e. licensing) (Kwak, 2002). In regards to the entrepreneur, Jeffry Timmons in his seminal book “*New Venture Creation*” evaluated the success of any entrepreneur during the value creation process hinges on he/she balancing the three components (Opportunity, Resources and Team) indicated in fig. 4 below

Fig 4: New Venture Creation: A Guide to Entrepreneurship (Timmons et al., 1985)

However, in relation to the success of a startup, (Bhave, 1994) elaborated on the key processes that startups go through in any value creation process, which are divided into three major stages.

1. Opportunity Stage
2. Technology Setup & Organization Creation Stage
3. Exchange Stage

Fig 5: Process model of entrepreneurial venture creation (Bhave, 1994)

Similar to (Timmons et al., 1985) model fig. 4, (Bhave, 1994) model fig. 5 has internally and externally influenced sequences during value creation processes. In both cases, opportunities must be fueled by a desire to act upon the identification of a business opportunity. Following the commitment to physical creation, entrepreneurs must be willing to take calculated personal and financial risks in order to acquire resources. Once an idea has been transformed into a product and delivered to the consumer or customer, the entrepreneurial process is complete. Subprocesses such as customer feedback and corrective action, if necessary, are then carried out (Bhave, 1994). This brings us to our final strategy “*Implement an agile operating model*” The process of developing new innovations will always be iterative. Agile approaches are more likely to succeed. As described in Deloitte's report (Kark et al., 2021), agile is all about developing new tools or processes in a stepwise manner by cross-functional teams (Kark et al., 2021).

Final Remarks

In most cases, the entrepreneur is the single most important determinant of the eventual success and evolution of any venture from startup to billion dollar. Understanding this enables us to make more informed, timely, and smarter decisions, which may lead to faster adaptation, bolder strategic choices, and long-term competitive advantage. Having a strategy on paper alone

is obviously insufficient; successful implementation is essential. Monitoring and making necessary adjustments to underlying strategic decisions and assumptions is necessary for an effective implementation of the entrepreneurial venture creation process.

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